

Implementation of Pancasila Ideology in Indonesian Educational Leadership: A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT: Pancasila plays an important role in responding to the times because the basic values of Pancasila can be developed in the life of the Indonesian nation. Pancasila is the basis of the Republic of Indonesia which is used as a reference in the nation and state. Pancasila as the foundation of nationality and state administration can be used as a solution to solve complex problems in terms of economic, social, political, cultural, educational, defense and security dimensions. The actualization of Pancasila values needs to be socialized, internalized and strengthened in its implementation, in the practice of national and state life by strengthening the character of the nation's generation in participating in building public understanding of national awareness. The Indonesian state needs a leader who can carry out his vision based on the values of Pancasila as a unifying tool for the nation. The values contained in the Pancasila ideology can be used as the basis for Indonesian education leadership. The values contained in Pancasila, whether God, Humanity, Unity, Consensus, and Justice, must be practiced and applied in the life of the nation, state and society in order to achieve the goals of education in Indonesia. Pancasila-characterized leadership will be able to guide the community towards the ideals of the state, and can be an intermediary in uniting the nation, and instilling the values of Pancasila in the Indonesian people.

KEYWORDS: Ideology, Educational, Leadership, Nation, Pancasila.

INTRODUCTION

Pancasila plays an important role in responding to the times because the basic values of Pancasila can be developed with Indonesian life. Pancasila is the basis of the Republic of Indonesia which is used as a reference in the nation and state (Raharja, 2019). The position of Pancasila as the basis of the Indonesian state has the consequence that the administration of the Indonesian state as a state of law (Gunawan, 2019). Pancasila as the foundation of nationality and state administration can be used as a solution to solve complex problems, both economic, social, political, cultural, educational, defense and security dimensions (Suharno, 2020). The actualization of Pancasila values needs to be socialized, internalized and strengthened in its implementation, in the practice of national and state life by strengthening the character of the nation's generation in participating in building public understanding of national awareness. The actualization of values in the practice of national and state life directs the existence of 3 values contained in the Pancasila ideology. The three values are: (Nugroho, Anam, Pudjiono, Rahardjo, & Sukarjono, 2020). 1. Basic values, namely principles, which are very abstract, very general in nature, not bound by time and place, with truth content like axioms. From the aspect of its value content, the basic value relates to the existence of something, which includes the ideals, goals, basic order and characteristics. 2. Instrumental value, which is a contextual value. Instrumental value is a description of the basic value, which is the direction of its performance for a certain period of time and for certain conditions. 3. The value of praxis, namely the value contained in everyday reality, in the form of how the people actualize the values of Pancasila.

For an ideology, the most important thing is the evidence of its practice or actualization in the life of society, nation and state. If the practical value cannot be actualized, then the ideology will lose its credibility. Pancasila is a critical and rational reflection as the basis of the state and the cultural reality of the nation, with the aim of obtaining the main points of understanding in a fundamental and comprehensive manner. Pancasila as an ideology both in terms of state ideology or national ideology is still maintained, especially as a basis for education. As a nation that already has a basic national consensus, often referred to as the "four pillars of nationality", Indonesia must continue to uphold Pancasila, the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, and Bhineka Tunggal Ika. Pancasila is a gift from God Almighty for the Indonesian nation as the glue of the nation, the foundation of the state, and the ideology of the state. The specialty of Indonesia from other nations is that the

Indonesian nation has Pancasila, which other nations in the world do not have, where only Indonesia has Pancasila, and that is the privilege and uniqueness of the Indonesian nation. Pancasila is the identity and identity of the Indonesian nation. any attempt to replace Pancasila with an ideology other than Pancasila is an act that denies the formation of Indonesia as a nation state, and for that it must be removed from the earth of Indonesia (Subagyo, 2020).

A leader is someone who is expected to have the ability to influence, give instructions and also be able to determine individuals to achieve organizational goals. A good leader is not seen from how many people become his followers, nor is it seen from how long he leads. A good leader is seen from how much he is able to create a new leader (Nurdina, 2020). The Indonesian state needs a leader who can carry out his vision based on the values of Pancasila as a unifying tool for the nation. Leadership with Pancasila character will be able to guide the community to pursue the ideals of the state, and can be an intermediary in uniting the nation, as well as instilling the values of Pancasila in the Indonesian people (Asmara & Conscience 2019).

Based on the description above, it is necessary to know more about "How is the Implementation of the Pancasila Ideology in Indonesian Educational Leadership?"

LITERATURE REVIEW

Implementation of Pancasila Ideology

Pancasila is considered as an ideology that has been established as a national principle in Indonesia, and has become the nation's view of life for the Indonesian nation. The ideological implementation of Pancasila is the national principle, carried out through character building, and has been started several years after Indonesian independence (Damanhuri & Raharja, 2019). Pancasila is a state ideology that is basically able to convey orientation, insight and normative guidelines in all areas of the life of the State (Putri, Charista, Lestari, & Trisiana, 2020). Historically, Pancasila was born as a national ideology taken from the values of local wisdom that grew and developed in Indonesia. As the ideology of the Indonesian nation, Pancasila was not born without strong historical roots. Many elements are contained in the noble values that are born from the points of the five precepts contained in Pancasila. Pancasila is the basic ideology of the Indonesian nation, namely as the values that underlie all aspects of the social life of the Indonesian people. Pancasila consists of five main joints, namely: (1) Belief in One Supreme God; (2) Just and civilized humanity; (3) the Indonesian Union; (4) Democracy led by solemn wisdom in representative deliberation; and (5) Social justice for all Indonesian people (Utama & Dewi, 2018).

Every country has its own ideology. In the life of the state, ideology is defined as a majority consensus about the basic values to be realized by establishing a state. Ideology for a country is very important. This is because the ideology adopted is believed to bring the nation-state towards prosperity and justice (Malik, 2020). The role of ideology is in line with the role of Pancasila as the ideology of the Indonesian state (Sobari, 2019). Pancasila has a role and function in the life of the nation and state. Its role and function is as the basis of the state, ideology and way of life of the nation. As the basis of the state, Pancasila functions to regulate all government processes and at the same time become the source of all sources of law (Wijaya, 2018). Pancasila was chosen as the ideology of the Indonesian nation because its values come from the original personality of the Indonesian nation itself. Pancasila has an important function and position in the Indonesian state, namely as the identity of the Indonesian nation, as the ideology of the Indonesian nation and state, as the basis of state philosophy, and as the principle of the unity of the Indonesian nation (Kristiono, 2017). Pancasila as a unifying tool of the nation has actually been in the hearts of every Indonesian, even long before independence. Pancasila is the guideline for living together in the life of the Indonesian nation. Pancasila strengthens the life of the nation and strengthens brotherhood among others in the social life of citizens (Adha & Susanto, 2020)

Indonesian Education Leadership

A leader is a person who has the ability to influence, give instructions and is also able to determine individuals or groups. Leaders play an important role in moving the people under them, their leadership skills must be good and effective so that they can build, encourage, and improve the quality of their subordinates' performance which has an impact on achieving the success of Indonesia's educational goals (Salsabila & Mukti, 2020). One of the success factors of a leader depends on the leadership technique used in creating a situation that causes the people he leads to raise awareness to carry out what is desired. In other words, whether or not a leader is effective depends on his ability to manage and apply his leadership pattern according to the situation and conditions of the organization (Kariyadi, 2017).

METHODS

This research can be categorized as a literature review research. The purpose of conducting a literature review is to obtain a theoretical basis that can support solving the problem being studied. The review process starts with a search engine, Google Scholar, to search for articles by keywords. "Implementation of Pancasila Ideology in Indonesian Educational Leadership". The search range was from 2017-2020 and identified a total of 50 studies and articles. The criteria for inclusion in this study were as follows:

Qualitative results of the Implementation of Pancasila Ideology in Indonesian Educational Leadership.

- Research conducted in Indonesia
- This research uses English
- Dissertations and theses are excluded

The steps in the Literature Review of each variable of the Implementation of the Pancasila Ideology in Indonesian Educational Leadership include:

Step1: Formulate the Problem

- Choose a topic that fits your issues and interests
- Problems must be written completely and accurately

Step 2: Searching the Literature

- Search literature relevant to research
- Get an overview (overview) of the research topic
- Sources of research resources are very helpful if they are supported by knowledge of the topic being studied.
- The sources provide an overview/summary of previous research.

Step 3: Data Evaluation

- Look at any contributions to the topics covered
- Search and find the right data sources as needed to support research
- Data can be in the form of quantitative data, qualitative data or data that comes from a combination of the two

Step 4: Analyze and Interpret

- Discuss and find and summarize literature

Table I. Implementation of Pancasila Ideology in Indonesian Educational Leadership

Author and Year of Publication	Title	Country	Methods	Sample	Results
Nugroho, et.al (2020).	Implementation of Ki Hajar Dewantara's Concept of Character Education Based on Pancasila Values for Millennial Generation Students	Indonesia	Qualitative Descriptive	-	The values contained in the ideology of Pancasila can be used as the basis for character education for students, especially the millennial generation, which in its implementation uses the concept of character education from Ki Hadjar Dewantara which includes the Among and Tri-Nga systems based on the tri-center of education, namely family, school and community.
Salsabila, & Mukti, (2020)	Application of Leadership to Achieve Organizational Progress (A Literature Study	Indonesia	Qualitative	-	Leadership has a very important role in an organization. Leaders in organizations have the ability to mobilize and direct their members to participate and contribute more to the organization.

Author and Year of Publication	Title	Country	Methods	Sample	Results
	on Leadership in Organizations)				
Sobari, (2019).	Problems from Ideology to Leadership: The Urgency of Revising the Public Service Law	Indonesia	Textual/docu mentary analysis	-	The principle of spirituality is important so that public services fulfill the spiritual rights of users and administrators and encourage the operation of public services with integrity. In order to guarantee publicness, a reorientation of public principles is needed in the implementation of public services that are bound by the values of Pancasila.
Damanhuri, & Raharja. (2019).	The Transformation of Character Ideology of Pancasila through Education	Indonesia	Qualitative	-	Finding out patterns of state intervention in the education system related to the Pancasila ideology.
Nurdina, (2020).	The Influence of Political Education on Student Leadership in Student Organizations at SMA Pasundan Cikalongkulon	Indonesia	Qualitative	-	Political education that is delivered to the younger generation, it is hoped that in the future, the younger generation will be aware of the rights and obligations as Indonesian citizens, appropriately the process of political education can shape and develop the leadership qualities of students in running student organizations.
Raharja, (2019).	The Relevance of Pancasila in the Era of Industry 4.0 and Society 5.0 in Vocational Higher Education	Indonesia	Qualitative	-	Revolution is closely related to technological innovation development, as well as the competence of Human Resources. So that Pancasila is very noble, it is important to participate in improving the capability of human resources, especially in terms of soft skills.

Author and Year of Publication	Title	Country	Methods	Sample	Results
Gunawan, (2019).	The Role of the State and the Implementation of Pancasila in Realizing a Welfare State in Indonesia.	Indonesia	Qualitative	-	The concept of a welfare state in Indonesia is the implementation of a welfare state that prioritizes the welfare of its citizens based on Pancasila which prioritizes social justice based on the principle of kinship with the principles of togetherness, efficiency with justice, environmental awareness, independence and maintaining a balance of progress and national economic unity as stipulated in the contents of the 1945 constitution.
Suharno, (2020).	The Urgency of Revitalizing Pancasila in Building National Character	Indonesia	Qualitative	-	The revitalization of Pancasila as the basis of the state implies that we must put Pancasila at its advantage with the opening of the 1945 Constitution.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section reports the main findings of the articles reviewed. The analysis shows that most of the articles focus on the Implementation of the Pancasila Ideology in Indonesian Educational Leadership. The articles that have been reviewed are research conducted in Indonesia

Based on the articles reviewed, there are various ways of collecting data related to the Implementation of the Pancasila Ideology in Indonesian Educational Leadership. The research method used is from article to article. The most commonly used method is by using interviews and observations used by (Nugroho, Anam, Pudjiono, Rahardjo, & Sukarjono, 2020), (Salsabila & Mukti, 2020), (Raharja, 2019), (Gunawan, 2019), (Suharno, 2020), and (Putri, Charista, Lestari, & Trisiana, 2020).

The values contained in the Pancasila ideology can be used as the basis for educational leadership. The values contained in Pancasila, whether God, Humanity, Unity, Consensus, and Justice, are practiced and applied in the life of the nation, state and society in order to achieve the goals of education in Indonesia. Pancasila must be the code of conduct, value system and system of the Indonesian education movement.

Research on the Implementation of Pancasila Ideology in Indonesian Educational Leadership has been carried out in Indonesia and has been carried out in various organizations. Table 1 shows that the research has been conducted in schools, universities, and schools. The results of the research mostly show that the Implementation of the Pancasila Ideology in Indonesian Educational Leadership

Leadership has a very important role in an organization. Leaders in organizations have the ability to mobilize and direct their members to participate and contribute more to the organization. The leader as an influential figure, must have a character based on the values of Pancasila in order to guide, to achieve the goals of education in Indonesia. These characters are in accordance with the values contained in Pancasila starting from the first to the fifth precepts. The values contained in the ideology of Pancasila can be used as the basis for character education for students, especially the millennial generation, which in its implementation uses the concept of character education from Ki Hadjar Dewantara which includes the Among and Tri-Nga systems based on the tri-center of education, namely family, school and community.

REFERENCES

1. Adha, M. M., & Susanto, E. (2020). Kekuatan Nilai-nilai Pancasila dalam Membangun Kepribadian Masyarakat Indonesia. *Al-Adabiya: Jurnal Kebudayaan dan Keagamaan*, 15(01), 121-138.
2. Asmara, A. L. W., & Nurani, F. (2019). Kepemimpinan Pancasila dalam Era Revolusi Industri 4.0 untuk Persatuan Indonesia.
3. Damanhuri, H., & Raharja, R. M. (2019). The Transformation of Character Ideology of Pancasila through Education. doi:10.21276 / sjhss.2019.4.4.8
4. Gunawan, B. (2019). Peran Negara dan Penerapan Pancasila Dalam Mewujudkan Negara Kesejahteraan (Welfare State) Di Indonesia. *Jurnal Paradigma Hukum Pembangunan*, 4(02), 115-127.
5. Kariyadi, D. (2017). Membangun Kepemimpinan Berbasis Nilai-Nilai Pancasila Dalam Perspektif Masyarakat Multikultural. *Citizenship Jurnal Pancasila Dan Kewarganegaraan*, 5(2), 86-96.
6. Kristiono, N. (2017). Penguatan Ideologi Pancasila Di Kalangan Mahasiswa Universitas Negeri Semarang. *Harmony*, 2(2), 193-204.
7. Malik, A. (2020). Membumikan Ideologi Pancasila Melalui Pendidikan Pancasila Sebagai Upaya Membangkitkan Nasionalisme. *EduTech: Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan dan Ilmu Sosial*, 6(1), 101-108.
8. Nugroho, S. S., Anam, M. C., Pudjiono, M. J., Rahardjo, M., & Sukarjono, B. (2020). Implementasi Konsep Pendidikan Karakter Ki Hajar Dewantara Berbasis Nilai-Nilai Pancasila Bagi Mahasiswa Generasi Mileneal. *YUSTISIA MERDEKA: Jurnal Ilmiah Hukum*, 6(2).
9. Nurdina, A. (2020). Pengaruh Pendidikan Politik Terhadap Kepemimpinan Peserta Didik pada Organisasi Kesiswaan Di Sma Pasundan Cikalongkulon. *Jurnal Pendidikan Politik, Hukum Dan Kewarganegaraan*, 10(1).
10. Putri, A. L., Charista, F. D. F., Lestari, S., & Trisiana, A. (2020). Implementasi Pancasila Dalam Pembangunan Dibidang Pendidikan. *TERAMPIL: Jurnal Pendidikan dan Pembelajaran Dasar*, 7(1), 13-22.
11. Raharja, H. Y. (2019). Relevansi pancasila era industry 4.0 dan society 5.0 di pendidikan tinggi vokasi. *Journal Of Digital Education, Communication, And Arts (Deca)*, 2(1), 11-20.
12. Salsabila, S., & Mukti, J. N. (2020). *Penerapan Kepemimpinan untuk Mencapai Kemajuan Organisasi (Sebuah Studi Literatur Tentang Kepemimpinan dalam Organisasi)*. Paper presented at the Prosiding Seminar Nasional LP3M.
13. Sobari, W. (2019). Problem Ideologi Hingga Kepemimpinan: Urgensi Revisi Undang-Undang Pelayanan Publik. *Jurnal Borneo Administrator*, 15(2), 137-158.
14. Subagyo, A. (2020). Implementasi Pancasila Dalam Menangkal Intoleransi, Radikalisme Dan Terorisme. *Jurnal Rontal Keilmuan PKn*, 6(1), 10-24.
15. Suharno, S. (2020). Urgensi Revitalisasi Pancasila dalam Membangun Karakter Kebangsaan. *JPK (Jurnal Pancasila dan Kewarganegaraan)*, 5(1), 23-33.
16. Utama, A. S., & Dewi, S. (2018). Pancasila Sebagai Ideologi Bangsa Indonesia Serta Perkembangan Ideologi Pancasila Pada Masa Orde Lama, Orde Baru, Dan Era Reformasi.
17. Wijaya, I. K. W. B. (2018). Revitalisasi Program Pedoman Penghayatan dan Pengamalan Pancasila (P4) Pada Jenjang Sekolah Dasar (SD) untuk Membentuk Generasi Emas 2045 Bermoral Pancasila. *Prosiding Nasional*.

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